

INFLUENCE OF THERMAL CYCLING ON COMPRESSIVE FATIGUE PROPERTIES
OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES

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Abstract

Compressive Fatigue behavior of quasi-isotropic T800/#3631 carbon/epoxy laminates is discussed in this paper. The laminate with a stacking sequence of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ are used for the present work. Compression fatigue test was performed with an electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine at a frequency of 10 Hz. The cyclic stress ratio ($R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$) was fixed to be 10. The comparisons of fatigue strength are made among the compression fatigue, tension fatigue and repeated tension and compression fatigue. A discussion is given on the master diagram showing the relationship between stress amplitude and mean stress for a given number of fatigue cycles. The effect of thermal cycling on the compressive fatigue lives is also discussed. The fixed value of lower temperature to be applied on the specimen in the thermal cycling test was -55°C , while the higher temperature was 125°C . Specimens were subjected to thermal cycling preliminarily to the proper number of cycles. Then the subsequent compressive fatigue resistance was evaluated to examine the effect of thermal cycling. As a result, it was found that the thermal cycling is not always deteriorates the compressive fatigue properties, but in some cases fatigue strength was improved by the moderate thermal cycling.

KEYWORD: Composites; Carbon/Epoxy; Fatigue; Quasi-Isotropic Laminates; Thermal Cycling.

1. Introduction

The majority of engineering structures are subjected to repeated loading. Consequently, designers require information about the fatigue properties of the material they use. Although much design data for the carbon fiber reinforced plastics under tension fatigue loading has been generated and much work has been reported on the fatigue failure mechanism, little

quantitative work has been conducted on the compressive fatigue properties of this materials. This may be partially due to the difficulty of preventing the buckling failure of laminates in axial compression fatigue testing. A lack of such a fatigue data gives rise to excessively conservative design and inefficient use of the material.

From aforementioned viewpoint, in the present work, compression fatigue test was first conducted on quasi-isotropic T800/#3631 carbon/epoxy laminate. Then comparative study was performed on the fatigue properties under three different loading conditions; repeated compressive loading, repeated tension loading and fully reversed pulsating loading. Discussion is given on the master diagram representing the relationship between stress amplitude and mean stress for various lives. In addition to this, investigation was made on the influence of thermal cycling on the compressive fatigue properties of the quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminate.

2. Samples and Experimental Method

The material used in the present study is a quasi-isotropic carbon fiber/epoxy laminate. The laminates were made from T800/#3631 prepregs where the reinforcement was the intermediate modulus/high strength carbon fiber, "Torayca" T800^H (Toray Co., Ltd., Japan) and the matrix was the 453K curable epoxy resin, #3631 (Toray Co.). The tensile properties of carbon fiber are listed in table 1. Laminates were fabricated by stacking eight prepreg sheets to obtain the sequence of [0/±45/90]_s. Curing cycle of

Table 1. Tensile properties of the carbon fiber.

Material	Tensile strength	Tensile modulus
"Torayca" T800 ^H	5586 MPa	2.94 × 10 ⁵ MPa

Fig.1. Curing cycle diagram.

laminate is shown in Figure 1. Fatigue tests were conducted under the three different loading conditions; repeated tension loading, repeated compression loading and fully reversed loading (repeated tension and compression). Cyclic stress ratio, R , representing a ratio of minimum stress to maximum stress was fixed to be 0.1, 10, -1 for respective fatigue testing of tension loading, compression loading and fully reversed loading. Fatigue tests were run at a frequency of 10Hz by a closed-loop electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine. Test pieces were kept in a chamber prior to testing under constant conditions of 296K in temperature and 65% in humidity.

Figure 2 illustrates the specimen configurations.

(a) Tension Fatigue

(b) Compression and Fully Reversed Fatigue

Fig.2. Fatigue test specimens.

3. Experimental Results and Discussion

3.1 S-N diagram Figure 3 shows the maximum cyclic stress, σ_{max} , plotted as a function of the number of cycles to fatigue failure under compression fatigue loading. The linear approximation between cyclic stress and fatigue life in semi-log scale is drawn by a solid line. The high fatigue resistance of the laminate tested is reflected in a very flat S-N diagram. This high tension fatigue performance will be recognized again by showing

Fig.3. S-N diagram for $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate under tension fatigue loading.

Fig.4. Relationship between normalized maximum cyclic stress and fatigue life.

figure 4 where the ordinate is the maximum cyclic stress normalized by the static tensile strength. It should be noted that the fatigue limit stress of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate exhibit about 72 percent. of static tensile strength, indicating the extremely high fatigue performance. It has been clearly observed in the side view of the laminate during fatigue testing that the delamination grows between plies especially at free edges in early stage of fatigue. Such a delamination does not immediately lead to catastrophic failure, but it extends the amount of interface damage gradually with increasing the fatigue cycles. The main fatigue failure mode has been observed to be progressive delamination occurred between plies. In $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate delamination grew from the edges at 45/90 interface[1]. Figure 5 shows the appearance of edge delamination observed in flat wise by the ultrasonic C-scan inspection. Dark portion in the figure is the delaminated area. The large increases in maximum strain

Fig.5. Ultrasonic inspection result on the flatwise of laminate.

Fig.6. S-N diagram for $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate under compression fatigue loading.

Fig.7. S-N diagram for $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate under fully reversed fatigue loading (zero mean stress).

occurs in early stage of fatigue, reflecting the large stiffness loss associated with interface edge delamination growth. It follows that the change of laminate stiffness is so rapid that the actual cyclic load applied on the specimen tends to decrease. Therefore a particularly designed load control device was used in the actual fatigue testing in order to keep a given constant stress value continuously until failure. In our previous work[1][2], We have performed replicate tests to characterize the scatter in cycles-to-failure. We pointed out that a three-parameter

Weibull distribution[3] gives a good fit to the tension fatigue life data for [0/±45/90]_s laminate.

Figures 6 and 7 show the S-N diagram for compression fatigue loading and fully reversed fatigue loading, respectively. Similarly to figure 4, the linear approximations between applied stress and fatigue life are indicated by solid lines. Comparison of fatigue S-N diagrams for tension fatigue, compression fatigue and fully reversed fatigue is provided in figure 8 by showing their linear approximations. It is very important to notice that there exists a large discrepancy in fatigue strength between tension fatigue and compression fatigue, although the slope of linear approximations of S-N diagram are almost the same. On the other hand, fatigue strength under fully reversed loading is the lowest and the slope of S-N diagram is slightly steeper, when compared with the other two cases.

Fig.8. Comparison of fatigue S-N diagrams for tension fatigue, compression fatigue and fully reversed fatigue.

3.2 Master diagram The master diagram showing the relationship between stress amplitude and mean stress for various lives is often considered to be the most desirable form of fatigue data in axial loading condition[4]. For metals the linear relationship

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_e \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_u} \right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

is commonly used, where σ_a and σ_m are stress amplitude and mean stress and σ_e is the fatigue strength at zero mean stress for the same life. σ_u is the static ultimate strength of the material. This is the Goodman law[5] and is used by designers to predict safe combination of mean stress and stress amplitude when the only experimental data available are for zero mean stress conditions. On the hand, Gerber law[6] assumes the parabolic relationship between stress amplitude and mean stress and expressed in the

form:

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_e \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_u} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (2)$$

Figure 9 is the master diagram produced from the fatigue test results in the present work. In Goodman law and Gerber law, the maximum fatigue strength is obtained under zero mean stress condition. However, figure 9 suggests that the fatigue strength shows the highest value when subjected to a moderate mean stress in the case of $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate. Similar phenomenon has been already reported on $[0/\pm 30]_{3S}$ AS/3501 laminate[7]. This phenomenon is probably brought by the low compressive fatigue strength in comparison with tensile fatigue strength associated with the material investigated.

Fig.9. Master diagram for $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate.

3.3 Influence of Thermal Cycling on Compressive Fatigue Properties

Thermal cycling testing apparatus used for this study contains two chambers, higher temperature chamber and lower temperature chamber. Higher temperature is fixed to be 125°C , while the lower temperature is fixed to be -55°C . As illustrated in figure 10, specimens were preliminarily subjected to thermal cycling between maximum temperature of

Fig.10. Thermal cycling program.

Fig.11. The influence of thermal cycling on compressive fatigue properties.

Photo.1. Fractured specimen under compressive fatigue loading.

125°C to be kept for thirty minutes and minimum temperature of -55°C to be kept for thirty minutes to the proper number of cycles. Then the specimens were used for the measurement of subsequent compressive fatigue strength to examine the influence of thermal cycling. The number of thermal cycling was changed in the three different ways, 15, 60 and 96 cycles. Figure 11 shows the compression fatigue test results for the samples after subjected to the thermal cycling to the three different numbers of cycles. It is interesting to note that the specimen shows the higher fatigue strength values than those of virgin material, when subjected to thermal cycling of 15 cycles and 60 cycles. The slope of linear approximation of S-N diagram is getting flat with an increase of numbers of thermal cycling. Finally, by the thermal cycling of 96 cycles compressive fatigue strength of the specimen was clearly decreased as a result of degradation of resin. The reason for an increase in fatigue strength by thermal cycling is considered to be due to the hardening effect in the surface of the specimen which was probably brought by the thermal cycling, just like a shot peening

treatment in metals.

Photograph 1 shows the appearance of fractured specimens. Fatigue failure mode for the sample after thermal cycling of 15 cycles is similar to that for virgin material. On the other hand, delamination damage is observed in the case of the sample after subjected to thermal cycling of 96 cycles. This is probably due to the degradation of resin matrix by thermal cycling.

4. Concluding Remarks

This investigation on the axial fatigue properties of quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminate led to the following conclusions:

1. Compressive fatigue strength is much lower, if compared with tension fatigue strength of the laminate investigated. This seems extremely important in the actual safe life design of composite structures. The highest fatigue strength was obtained in the tension fatigue test and compressive fatigue strength followed in the next. Fatigue strength in fully reversed loading test was the lowest.
2. In the master diagram representing the relationship between stress amplitude and mean stress, maximum stress amplitude was obtained in the location of tension mean stress side, unlike the conventional materials.
3. By the thermal cycling of 96 cycles compressive fatigue strength of the specimen was clearly decreased. However, it was found that the thermal cycling does not always provide the bad effect on the compressive fatigue strength, but in some cases, particularly when subjected to thermal cycling of 15 cycles compressive fatigue resistance of the sample was improved.

5. REFERENCES

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